

National Harvest Mouse Survey

RESULTS FROM SECOND SURVEY

2022-2023

The Mammal Society's National Harvest Mouse Survey

Results from the Second Survey, 2022-2023

Coomber, F.G., Clifton, R, Gilford, E., Alizan, A., Crawley, D., Kirk, S., Lloyd, A.J. & Gurnell, J. (2023).
The Mammal Society's National Harvest Mouse Survey: Results from the Second Survey, 2022-2023.
The Mammal Society.

About the Mammal Society

Established in 1954, the Mammal Society strives for a future in which sustainable mammal populations thrive as part of healthy and diverse ecosystems benefiting people and nature across the British Isles and Ireland.

- We work to ensure a bright future for mammals in the British Isles by inspiring, informing, supporting and enhancing conservation projects and policies that protect and restore native mammal populations and their habitats
- We empower conservationists, students, citizen scientists and nature champions to play a key role in mammal conservation now and in the future through providing training, resources and survey activations
- We seek to build public awareness of and support for mammal conservation through education, communications and campaigns

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Executive Summary

Background

The harvest mouse (*Micromys minutus*: Pallas, 1771) is Britain's smallest rodent. The recent review by The Mammal Society of the population and conservation status of British mammals (Mathews, 2018) indicated that our understanding of the numbers and distribution of harvest mice across England, Scotland and Wales was uncertain because of a lack of robust data. To address this, in 2021 The Mammal Society established a national survey of harvest mice using a standard protocol to be carried out by volunteers. The survey is based on searching for harvest mouse nests between the months of October and March. Because harvest mouse numbers fluctuate considerably within and between years in response to factors such as food availability and weather, it is intended that national surveys should be carried every year for several years.

The first survey was carried out by a dedicated community of volunteers across different habitats within England, Scotland and Wales in 2021-22. The findings from this survey are reported by Coomber *et al.* 2023 and Lloyd *et al.* 2023. The second survey was carried out in 2022-2023 and the results from this survey, and comparisons with the first survey, are reported here.

Key findings

- Survey effort increased considerably from the first to the second year with 31 regional coordinators (up from 19 in first year), 59 groups (up from 28), and an estimate of 292 surveyors (up from 184) taking part. In total, 843 surveys and 2,580 person-hours of searching were carried out in 2022-23, an increase from 584 surveys and 1,432 person-hours of searching in 2021-2022 respectively. This demonstrates an increase in interest and commitment by volunteers and volunteer groups and is encouraging for future surveys.
- Following from the increase in surveyor participation, a broader area was surveyed in 2022-23 than 2021-22 with 394 hectads and 672 tetrads covered. Three hundred and seventy-seven presence-only records and information on 2,091 nests were collected. Impressively, the presence of harvest mice was detected in 80.0% of the hectads and 72.8% of the tetrads surveyed. This suggested a widespread distribution of these creatures across various habitats.
- By amalgamating the findings from both survey years, a more comprehensive picture of harvest mouse distribution emerged. It was found that 18.42% of all hectads and 1.74% of tetrads contained information about harvest mice. This enrichment of the data further contributes to our understanding of their nationwide distribution.
- One hundred and fifty-four hectads and 135 tetrads were monitored in both survey years. Presence in both years confirmed in 144 hectads (74.03%) and 82 tetrads (1.74%) indicating healthy and persistent populations in the surveyed areas. Twelve hectads and 17 tetrads did not detect harvest mice in either survey year.

Consideration for the future

Despite the increase in geographical coverage across the country in the second survey, there are still some regions where more data on presence or non-detections would be valuable. These include Scotland, north-west England and north and central Wales.

Repeat surveys or surveys at adjacent sites in the future will provide further insights on year-to-year fluctuations in the spatial distribution and numbers of harvest mice.

Extensive volunteer involvement is key to the success of the National Harvest Mouse Survey (NHMS). As evident from other long-term mammal monitoring programmes such as the NBMP (National Bat Monitoring Programme) and the NDMP (National Dormouse Monitoring Programme), standardised sampling designs and adequate volunteer training are necessary, and it is hoped that as the NHMS continues the data collected will encourage additional, more specific studies to be carried out. In relation to reintroducing harvest mouse as a conservation initiative, it is advisable to conduct thorough surveys of potential release sites for a minimum of two years before any harvest mouse releases are undertaken.

The 2022-2023 survey for the first time looked at nest colour to assess whether nests found were active nests, which could provide information on breeding times both within and, in the future, between years. The data were few and inconclusive and it is recommended that more effort should be made to look at this in the future. Data collected on nest dimensions and plant species used to construct nests were collected but are not reported here.

Between August 2022 and March 2023, the NHMS was heavily promoted through social media and in the Society's magazine and E-bulletin. A feedback questionnaire was circulated to all participants after the survey. Although the number of returns was not large, the responses of surveyors and coordinators offered a comprehensive overview of their experiences and perspectives, highlighting areas of success and potential improvement for future survey initiatives.

Together, the two survey years collectively enriched our knowledge of harvest mice and their distribution. The dedication of surveyors, the extensive hours invested, and the meticulous data collection all contributed to a more comprehensive understanding of these fascinating creatures and their role in the ecosystem.

Photo by Philip Orris
Highly Commended in Mammal Photographer of the Year 2023

Acknowledgements

We would sincerely like to thank all our volunteer surveyors, and to all local mammal groups, wildlife groups and other organisations that have contributed data to this survey, either directly through staff and volunteer members conducting surveys on or near your grounds, or indirectly, where permissions have been given for volunteers outside of your networks to conduct surveys on your estates.

A huge thank you to:

Bedfordshire Mammal Group, Berkshire Mammal Group, British Wildlife Centre, Buckinghamshire Mammal Group, Cambridge Mammal Group, Chester Zoo, Coombe Mill volunteers, Cornwall Mammal Group, Crowhurst Environmental Group, Cumbria Mammal Group, Derbyshire Mammal Group, Devon Mammal Group, Dorset Wildlife Trust, Durham Wildlife Trust, Environment Agency, Essex Wildlife Trust, Flamingoland, Frampton Cotterell Nature, Friends associated with Great Haughurst Copse, Friends of Coombe Valley, Gibside National Trust, Gwent Wildlife Trust, Hereford Mammal Group, Herts and Middlesex Wildlife Trust, Humane Wildlife Solutions, Inaturalist, iRecord, Kent Mammal Group, Moor Meadows volunteers, National Trust, National Trust East Devon, North Wales Wildlife Trust, Northam Burrows vols, Northumberland Wildlife Trust, Oxfordshire Mammal Group, PBHCT, Plumpton & East Chiltington Wildlife Group, Quantock landscape partnership scheme, Royal Horticultural Society, Scottish Wildlife Trust, Shropshire Mammal Group, Somerset Mammal Group, South West Lakes Trust, Staffordshire Mammal Group, Surrey Hills Society, Sussex Mammal Group, Sussex Wildlife Trust, Test Valley Borough Council, The Friends of Hastings Country Park Nature Reserve and Groundwork South, Wakehurst Kew Gardens, Wansbeck Natural History

Society, Wildfowl & Wetlands Trust, Wiltshire Mammal Group, Worchester Wildlife Trust, Worsbrough Mill and Yealm-Erme farmers group.

However, most importantly we would like to thank all the following people for submitting data to the survey. We have strived to include everyone but as an observer's name was not requested it is possible that this following list is not exclusive:

A. Hunt, Adam Burrough, Adam Rhodes, Adam Woolcott, Alan Wilkinson, Alex Jamieson, Alice Beaney, Alice Whitaker, Alison Leaf, Alistair Homer, Amanda Dobbs, Amanda Lloyd, Andrew Cooper, Andrew Helyer, Andrew Jennings-Giles, Andrew Rothwell, Andrew Wadds, Andy Gattiker, Ann Gleave, Anna Daniels, Anne-Marie Jones, Anne-Marie Richard, B.Mossop, Ben Arkless, Ben Mapp, Ben Stammers, Brian Heppenstall, Bryony Tolhurst, Caitlin Bowman, Cat Frampton, Cath Myatt, Catherine Sankey, Cathy Woodhouse, Charlie Long, Charlotte Chetwynd, Charlotte Mead, Chris Chapman, Chris Elsdon, Chris Jones, Christa Emmett, Clare Fiennes, Clarelw, Daisy Meadowcroft, Dan Townsend, Dave Groves, Dave Lewns, David Dunham, David Hanks, David Hill, David Phillips, Debra Goldsmith, Dennis Harding, Derek Crawley, Di Hall, Diana Atkinson, Diane Comley, Ed Dolphin, Edward Carroll, Elaine Burnell, Elaine Green, Elizabeth Durrant, Ellie Benjamin, Ellie Rickman, Ellie Sherwin, Ellie Smith, Emily Gilford, Emily MacAllister, Emily Yetman, Emily Yokouchi, emily-11, Emma Reece, Emma Scotney, Fenn Doggett, Fern Oscroft, Filia Stuart-jervis, Fiona Haynes, Fiona Wistow, firestormrider, Frances Whistler, Francis Ware, Frazer Coomber, Fred Eason, Gareth Harris, Gemma Milner, George Hogg, Georgia M, Gill Smart, Glyn Horn, Graham Smith, graham-3, Hannah Barlow, Hazel Greenland, Heath Nickels, Heather Sunderland, Helen Peake, Henry Cook, Hester Stanwood, Hetha, Hilary Marshall, Hope Nothhelfer, hydra101, Ian Bond, Ian Burnell, Ines Pender, Isobel Girvan, Isobel Refoy, Izzy Ponsford, Izzy Williamson, Jack Gradidge, Jack Riggall, Jackie Gage, Jacqueline Watkinson, James Cartwright, James Martin, James Montague, Janet Bond, Jasmine Dooney, Jem Jacob Gibson, Jennie Showers, Jennifer Palmer, Jenny Lines, Jenny Tratt, Jeremy Denton, Jess Smallcombe, Jill Ferguson, Jill Tyson, Jo Pullin, Joanna Athey, Joe Knights, Joe Malyan, Joe Newberry, Joerg Niehoegen, John Hickson, John Martin, John Sharpe, John Steer, John Walters, Jon Gardner, Jon Steward, Jonathan Woodcock, Jonathan Woodcock, Josh Kalms, Julian Small, Julie Jamieson, Julie Straw, Juno1, Karen Barnard, Karen Pilkington, Karen Shaw, Kate Blincoe, Kath Thorne, Katharine Garratt, Katherine Moore, Keith Lightfoot, Kelly O'Sullivan, Kelly Sheldrick, Ken Winder, Keri Lloyd, Kevin Newell, Kevin Pressland, Kieran Holliday, Kim Greaves, Kim J Melhuish, Knowleswift, Kristin Thompson, ky-drake, Ladywalk NR, Laura Fairs, Lauren Gorman, Laurie Jackson, Leitza Gorman, Linda Clark, Linda Gerrard, Linda Nottage, Lisa Wade, Liz Hamling, Liz Trotman, Liz Williams, Lorna Phillips, Lorraine Ashley, Lorraine Jenkins, Louisa Kilgallen, Lucy Buckingham, Lucy King, Lucy Pendrick, Luke Nelson, l-vokes, Lydia Farnell, Lynn Whitfield, Lynne Lambert, Macauley Anderson, Maggie Watson, Mariko Whyte, Mark French, Mark Hows, markswt, Martin Devine, Mary Breeds, Matt Butters, Matt Collis, Matthew Scarborough, Max Pillings, Meg Vallender, Michael Banks, Michelle Jeal, Michelle McGinn, Mick Bandle, Mick Sherwin, Mike Dunks, Mike Harvey, Mike Pearey, Monique Scott, Nathan Walton, Neil Nash, Neil Williams, Nicholas Weston, Nick Mott, Pamela Mynott, Pascal Bisson, Paul Bushell, Paul Jeffery, Paul Otto, Paul Wright, Penny Bridle, Pete Cooper, Pete Thompson, Peter Cooper, Peter Findley, Phil Carter, Pippa Keynes, Polly Godfrey, Rachel Spencer, Rebecca Middleton, Richard Power, Richard Wilson, Richard Winspear, Rob Mackeen, Rob Nottage, Roger Bloxham, Roger Halsey, Ron Hughes, Rosie Stone, Ross Clifton, Ross D. Baker, Rowan Duckworth, Rowena Millar, Rupert Hawley, Ruth Angravr, Ryan Paddock, Sarah Butcher, Sarah Jupp, Sarah Norman, Sarah Wilson-frost, sarahetf, Sharon Barkley, Sharon Kimber, Sheelagh Halsey, Shioban Pryke, Shirley Robert, Simon H, Simon Smart, Simon Thurgood, Simon Wicks, skirretroot, Sophie Webb, Sophie Webster, Stephen Robinson, Steve Kirk, Steve Masters, Stuart Moore, Sue Allison, Sue Collins, Sue

Cooper, Sue Elsdon, Sunny Jones, Susan Green, Terry Coult, thewhisperingwild, Tim Hayward, Tom Hill, Trevor Fletcher, Vivien Kent, Wendy Tagg and wheretheroesestwine.

We apologise if anyone has inadvertently been left out.

Funding

Specific regions and coordinators were partially or fully funded for their work through external funding. The harvest mouse surveys and coordinator roles for Steve Kirk in Kent were funded by the Kent Mammal Group and for Sarah Butcher from Devon Mammal Group's Harvest Mouse Project, by the People's Postcode Lottery awarded from the People's Postcode Trust. The Mammal Society staff time associated with this survey was covered by the Mammal Society's core costs provided primarily by Mammal Society memberships and donations.

Glossary of Terms

2021-22 Survey – The term used to describe the results and data from the first survey year conducted between the beginning of October 2021 and the end of March 2022.

2022-23 Survey – The term used to describe the results and data from the latest survey year conducted between the beginning of October 2022 and the end of March 2023.

Survey – a record with location, harvest mouse nest numbers and information on effort, specifically duration spent looking for harvest mice and number of people searching.

Survey effort – In the terms of this survey effort or survey effort is recorded as people hours or the multiplication of the number of people and the duration that they spent search for harvest mouse nests during a survey.

Presence-only – A record of harvest mouse presence or absence that does not include any information on survey effort.

Hectad – a 10 by 10 km British Ordnance Survey National Grid square presented using the British National Grid projection system (ESPG: 27700).

Tetrad – a 2 by 2 km British Ordnance Survey National Grid square presented using the British National Grid projection system (ESPG: 27700).

Acronyms

BIAZA – British and Irish Association of Zoos and Aquariums

BNG – British National Grid

GDPR – General Data Protection Regulation

LMG – Local Mammal Group

LRC – Local Records Centre

NBMP - National Bat Monitoring Programme

NBN – National Biodiversity Network

NDMP - National Dormouse Monitoring Programme

NHMS – National Harvest Mouse Survey

NPHSE – Nests Per Hour of Survey Effort

MISE - Mammals in a Sustainable Environment

TMS – The Mammal Society

UKCEH – UK Centre for Ecology and Hydrology

WVC – Watsonian Vice County

Introduction

The harvest mouse (*Micromys minutus*: Pallas, 1771) is Britain's smallest rodent. It has a typical adult body weight of 6 grams (range 5-9 g) and is well adapted to life in tall grasses with supporting vegetation (e.g. docks, thistles, brambles) which they inhabit year-round. Various surveys of the distribution of harvest mice in Britain have been carried out in the last 50 years, for example, in the 1970s (Harris, 1979), the 1990s (Pain, 1997), and 2014 (White, 2014). Other multi-species surveys, which also included surveying for harvest mice took place in 2013 (Toms, 1999), and in 2011 – 2015 (Tapping, 2013). More recent surveys exist, but these were typically confined to local areas (e.g., Kent (Kirk, 2021) and Essex (Dobson, 2012)). Historical harvest mouse distributions from previous surveys are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 The reported historical distributions of harvest mice: left - the 1970s national survey (Harris, 1979), centre - the Atlas of the Mammals from Britain and Northern Ireland (Crawley *et al.*, 2020), and right - the Review of the Population and Conservation Status of British Mammals (Mathews *et al.*, 2018).

The 1990s survey highlighted areas of decline from the 1970s survey; harvest mouse nests were only reported in 29% of the 300 repeated sites from the original surveyed areas (Sargent and Pottie, 1997, Sargent, 1999). The most recent Atlas of the Mammals of Great Britain and Northern Ireland has also identified 138 fewer presence hectads from the most recent reporting period, 2000-2016, compared to the historic period, 1960-1992 (Crawley *et al.*, 2020).

Furthermore, an analysis into the use of biological records to deduce long-term occupancy trends (the proportion of sites or areas occupied by the species) found occupancy decreased from 1970 to 2016, suggesting that this species' distribution has declined over time (Coomber *et al.*, 2021). Despite evidence of national declines in distribution, examples of local surveys from Kent, Warwickshire, and Essex found harvest mice were locally widespread with presences recorded in a large percentage of hectads (Wildlife World Autumn 2016 by PTES - https://issuu.com/ptes/docs/ww10_full_reduced_size, Dobson, 2012, Kirk, 2021).

The Review of the Population and Conservation Status of British Mammals (Mathews *et al.*, 2018) estimated the population size of harvest mice (566,000) from the ratio of harvest mice to wood mice which is a far from satisfactory method; as a result it was concluded that trends in population size are unclear.

All-in-all, it was concluded that there was a need for more comprehensive and robust data on the numbers and distribution of harvest mice in Britain.

To address this, the Mammal Society developed a National Harvest Mouse Survey (NHMS) protocol in 2021. For the full rationale and background to the NHMS see Coomber *et al.* 2023 and Lloyd *et al.* 2023.

The survey is based on searching for harvest mouse nests; this is a non-invasive way of determining the presence of harvest mice that can be carried out by volunteer surveyors. Harvest mice build characteristic spherical nests of woven grass. Breeding nests can be up to 10 cm in diameter whereas non-breeding nests are usually smaller. Freshly made nests are initially green but turn brown as the vegetation dies.

The survey aimed to:

- I. develop a monitoring strategy,
- II. create a community of surveyors,
- III. promote recording,
- IV. present harvest mice as ecological indicators of agricultural landscapes, and
- V. assess the current population and conservation status of harvest mice in Britain.

Volunteer surveyors from across the country were asked to conduct nest search surveys at sites within their local area supported by volunteer regional coordinators at any time between October and March (incl.). Since harvest mouse numbers fluctuate considerably within and between years in response to factors such as food availability and weather (Trout 1978; Lloyd & Kirk, 2021), knowledge obtained from a one-off survey in a particular location is likely to be misleading, and therefore it is intended that the survey should be repeated every year for several years.

The first survey took place in 2021-2022. Information on where they searched, how many people were looking, for how long, the habitat and the number of harvest mice nests found were recorded. The survey was promoted across several media platforms, with protocols, training materials, and information provided via a dedicated webpage ([National Harvest Mouse Survey – The Mammal Society](#)).

The first NHMS 2020-2021 was successful in recording harvest mice nests with over 900 records collected from surveys and presence-only records and generally increased the available data on this species. The survey achieved good geographical coverage with a wide national extent (covering England, Scotland, and Wales), but gaps in the geographical distribution of surveys meant that a full understanding of the distributional status of this species was not possible. However, a high reconfirmation presence rate indicated that harvest mouse populations were persisting well at sites within their historical range but the finding of harvest mouse nests beyond the historical reference dataset suggests the species maybe be under-recorded elsewhere in Britain (see Coomber *et al.* 2023, Lloyd *et al.* 2023).

The second NHMS took place between October 2022 and March 2023 with aims to:

- I. Grow the community of surveyors and coordinators,
- II. Increase geographical coverage of harvest mice records and surveys,
- III. Compare the findings from the first and second survey years to evaluate whether the monitoring strategy can identify changes in harvest mouse populations,
- IV. Provide information on the population and conservation status of harvest mice across Britain.

Methods

Data collection and handling in the second year of the harvest mouse survey (2022-2023) followed along similar lines to those in the first year (2021-2022), details of which can be found in Coomber et al. 2023 and Lloyd et al. 2023.

Survey Protocol

The second year of the National Harvest Mouse Survey took place from October 2022 to March 2023. During this time, volunteers were asked to look for harvest mouse nests in suitable habitats, such as tall, tussocky grass. They were asked to record where they searched, the type of habitat they searched, how many people were searching, and for how long. It was also important for them to record the number of nests they found or if they did not find any. Additionally, they were asked to provide more details about the nests they found, such as their exact locations, size, height above the ground, the height of the surrounding plants, and the types of plants present. Even though the survey did not specifically ask for records of nests without information about the survey effort, these presence-only records were collected and used to help provide presence classifications.

To assist surveyors, they were directed to the project's website (<https://www.mammal.org.uk/science-research/harvest-mouse-project>) where they could access a survey guide and could connect with local coordinators or experienced surveyors in their region. The guide provided detailed information on where and when to search, how to recognize suitable habitats, how to find and identify harvest mouse nests, and how to document and send in data. While the guide was quite similar to the one from the previous survey season, some small changes were made based on feedback. For instance, there was a greater focus on noting the colour of the nests found (brown, mixed, or green) to see if useful information could be obtained on the time of nest building. Before starting this year's survey, communication with regional coordinators took place to highlight the repeat survey's aims. These goals included to survey new areas and to identify sites for repeat surveys from the first 2021-2022 survey.

Data Collection

Survey participants were asked to submit harvest mouse survey data and presence-only records (records of harvest mouse presence that did not include survey effort associated information) to The Mammal Society's national harvest mouse coordinator during or shortly after the end of the survey season. The data collected by regional coordinators were collated into an excel recording form template and passed to the national coordinator. However, data could also be submitted directly using The Mammal Society's recording app, Mammal Mapper (www.mammal.org.uk/volunteering/mammal-mapper) or the online recording platform (www.mammal.org.uk/science-research/harvest-mouse-project), through the use of third party recording apps – iRecord (irecord.org.uk) or iNaturalist (www.inaturalist.org), and directly via email to the Mammal Society.

Data from the sources above were compiled into a database, alongside data collected from the initial survey season, for the purpose of report writing and analyses. The data used for this report were those collected on or before the 1st of July 2023.

It should be noted that the results from the first survey season (2021-2022) might show some very slight differences compared to those initially reported (see references above) because of the inclusion of additional data collected after the initial report writing deadline, and the removal of a few records during the verification process.

Current status

To assess the current status of harvest mice, their combined presence classifications across the two survey years were compared to a historical reference dataset, the Atlas of Mammals from Great Britain and Northern Ireland (Crawley *et al.* 2020). The historical data were compared to the identified presence and non-detections, at a hectad resolution, of harvest mice from the combined survey years. The combined survey presence classifications were based on both years with a presence classification based on harvest mice being present in at least one of the survey years. A combined non-detection classified was recorded if there were no presence data in either year.

Short-term assessments of distribution were identified by comparing the two survey years at both a hectad, tetrad, and site-based resolutions. It was therefore possible to identify the number and percentage of these spatial units which continued, gained, or lost harvest mice between the survey years.

Temporal Trends

To analyse temporal trends, comparisons were made between the first and second survey years. This included the calculation of three indices: mean number of nests per survey, occupancy, and Nests Per Hour of Survey Effort (NPHSE). The mean number of nests per survey was calculated by averaging out the number of nests without considering survey effort. Occupancy was calculated as the proportion of surveys with reported presence. NPHSE was calculated as the mean across all surveys of the number of nests divided by the individual survey effort based on people hours (see Coomber *et al.*, 2023, Lloyd *et al.* 2023).

These indices are affected by the inclusion of new areas surveyed during the second year (2022-2023). Therefore, the indices were compared in two ways: using all surveys and using surveys from areas which were surveyed in both years.

Nest colour

During the second survey (2022-2023), participants were asked to note the colour of nests, specifically whether they were brown or green to give an indication of active, nests. This information was to be included in individual nest records, both for presence-only records and for detailed survey records. For the nests observed during the first survey (2021-2022) and those from the second survey (2022-2023) where colour information was missing, colours were assigned based on any accompanying comments within the data available. Nests described using terms such as "brown," "empty," "abandoned," "unoccupied," or "disused" were categorised as brown. Nests described as "occupied" were classified as green. Some nests were denoted as having a mix of colours, for example, both green and brown, but for analytical purposes, these were considered as green. Every recorded nest from the presence-only records and the survey-associated records was assigned a colour, where feasible. Subsequently, the frequency of each nest colour was examined for each month of the survey.

Nest dimensions and plant species

Information collected about nest dimensions and plant species supporting nests is not included in this report but will be analysed and reported at a later date.

Survey promotion and feedback

Information on the promotion of the 2022-2023 survey was gathered by TMS staff in the lead up to the survey which started in October 2022. In addition, as was done after the 2021-22 survey, surveyor and coordinator questionnaires were circulated following the 2022-23 survey to everyone involved to provide feedback and suggestions for developing the survey moving forward (for details of the questionnaire, see Coomber *et al.* 2023). To help estimate the number of participants, the feedback forms from coordinators were used.

Results

Numbers of surveys and nests found in 2022-2023 survey year

A country and county level breakdown of the data, results, and calculated indices can be found at <https://tinyurl.ph/avGqa>.

Country breakdowns of the survey can be found in Appendix 1.

- During the second survey year (October 2022 to March 2023), a total of **843 surveys** were conducted that recorded **1,593 nests**.
- Of these nests, 972 (61%) had detailed information, including their exact positions, nest heights and diameters, and information about the plant species and habitat where they were found.
- Additionally, there were **377 presence-only records** (records lacking information on survey effort) with a total count of **498 nests**.

This means that a total of **2,091 nests** were counted during the second survey year.

Surveyor and coordinator participation 2021-2022 and 2022-2023

On average, each survey during the second year involved **3.5 people** and lasted for approximately **52.4 minutes**. The total duration of all surveys combined was **378 hours**. The survey effort, measured as the number of people hours (i.e., the survey duration multiplied by the number of people conducting the survey), averaged 3.5 people hours. Across the entire season, the total survey effort amounted to **2,580 people hours** (Table 1).

There was a notable increase in the number of regional coordinators, from 19 in 2021-2022 to 31 in 2022-23. These coordinators covered not only several new regions but also continued to oversee regions from the first survey year, showing growth and expansion in the programme's reach.

A total of 59 local mammal groups, wildlife organizations, and other relevant groups contributed to the collection and submission of harvest mice data at the time of report writing. Among the surveys and presence-only records submitted, 292 individuals were identified as the surveyors or observers who had collected and submitted data on harvest mice (Table 1). So, in all, there was a marked increase in the amount of data collected and the level of participation during the in the second survey (2022-2023) compared with the first survey (2021-2022). The only exception to this trend is the number of presence-only records (Table 1).

Table 1 Comparison of participation and amount of data collected for the two harvest mouse survey seasons.

	2021-2022 Survey Season	2022-2023 Survey Season	Inter- seasonal change
Number of regional coordinators	19	31	UP
Estimate of involved groups	28	59	UP
Estimate of participating surveyors (named observers)	184	292	UP
Number of surveys conducted	584	843	UP
Number of presence-only records recorded	439	377	DOWN
Total survey effort in people hours	1,432	2,580	UP

Geographical coverage

During the second survey year (2022-23), survey information and presence-only records were gathered from a total of **394 (13.6% of all) hectads and 672 (1.09%) tetrads** across Great Britain (Figure 2, Table 2).

By analysing these data, it becomes evident that in the 2022-23 survey, approximately **80.39% of surveyed hectads and 72.77% of surveyed tetrads** could be categorised as having harvest mice present (Table 2).

Considering both the first and second survey years combined (Figure 3), the information on harvest mouse presence across Great Britain is based on 73 (80.22%) of all counties, 531 (18.42% of all) hectads, and 1,071 (1.74% of all) tetrads. Among the surveyed hectads and tetrads, approximately 80.04% and 71.90% respectively were classified as having harvest mice presence (Table 2).

Table 2 The number of spatial units (counties, hectads and tetrads) with collected harvest mouse information from the two harvest mouse survey seasons. Repeated information on presence included the use of both survey and presence-only record data. Repeated survey information is identified using only data from surveys.

	2021- 2022 Survey	2022- 2023 Survey	Combined survey	Repeated Presence	Repeated Survey
Number of counties with information	63	63	73	53	36
Number of hectads with presence information	292	394	531	154	98
Percentage of monitored hectads with harvest mouse presence	76.40%	80.40%	80.04%	NA	
Number of tetrads with information	534	672	1,071	135	86
Percentage of monitored tetrads with harvest mouse presence	67.98%	72.77%	71.90%	NA	

Current status of harvest mice in Britain

Using the Atlas of Mammals from Great Britain and Northern Ireland (Crawley *et al.*, 2020) and associated data as a reference dataset, the historically known harvest mouse distribution was compared from the identified hectads with presence and non-detection information from the combined two years of survey (2021-2022 and 2022-2023).

Of the 990 atlas hectads with time-period presence information of harvest mice, 382 (38.59% of historic reference) have been monitored over the last two survey years, with a further 149 hectads monitored beyond this extent (Table 3). Although this has improved the coverage from last year's survey (198, 20% of historic reference, see Coomber *et al.* 2023) it is still only a proportion of the previous known distribution of harvest mice and indicates that the **status results should continue to be classified as data deficient**.

Table 3 The comparison between the combined survey results from 2021 and 2022 against the Atlas of the Mammals of Great Britain and Northern Ireland historical reference dataset.

Combined survey results	Historic (1960-1992)	Combined			Total
		(1960-1992 & 2000-2016)	Recent (2000-2016)	Previously unreported	
Presence	83	180	62	100	425
Non-detection	18	27	12	49	106
Total	101	207	74	149	531

While the distributional status of harvest mice in Great Britain cannot be reliably concluded at this time, the comparison with the historic reference dataset does provide some indication towards their population status.

Of the known hectads to have ever been occupied by harvest mice **85.08% have been reidentified as present** in the last two years. This provides quite a strong indication that harvest mice populations across their historic range at relatively coarse scales are persisting to the present time.

Furthermore, the survey results from the extralimital area of the historic reference dataset were two-third (67.11%) identified as presence. This could indicate that the harvest mouse national range has increased in the last few years, or more likely that harvest mice populations have previously gone under-recorded in these areas in the past (Table 3, Figure 4).

Figure 4 The comparison between the 2021-2022 and 2022-2023 survey years identified presence (green circles) and non-detections (red circles) and the Atlas of Mammals from Britain and Northern Ireland historical reference dataset (sites).

Repeatedly monitored spatial units

As previously established, there were a total of 154 hectads and 134 tetrads with harvest mice present. This classification was based on both survey data and presence-only information from the two survey years. The spatial distribution of the identified presence repeat sites encompassed at least one repeat site from each country and included over 30 different counties. This ensured a comprehensive representation across a wide geographical area (Figure 5). Among the hectads where presence was identified during the 2021-22 survey year, a total of 114 (74.04%) were reaffirmed as having presence during the second year, 2022-23 (Table 3). Furthermore, 19 hectads initially marked as absence in the first year (2021-22) were subsequently reclassified as having harvest mice present during the second survey year (2022-23). Regarding the tetrads, approximately 60.74% of those with presence in the 2021-22 year maintained their presence status in 2022-23. Additionally, 18 tetrads that were previously classified as absence were re-designated as having presence during the second survey year (Table 4 and Figure 5).

Table 4 The number of continued presence and non-detections in 2021-22 and 2022-23

	Hectads	Tetrads
Number monitored in both years	154	135
2021-22 presence and 2022-23 presence	114	82
2021-22 presence and 2022-23 non-detection	9	18
2021-22 non-detection and 2022-23 presence	19	18
2021-22 non-detection and 2022-23 non-detection	12	17

Figure 5 The tetrads with harvest mouse presence classifications from both the 2021 and 2022 survey years. Continued presence identifies the tetrads which were classified as present in both years, Gain of Presence indicates where a non-detection in 2021 was a presence in 2022, Loss of Presence indicates where a presence in 2021 was a non-detection in 2022 and continued non-detection indicates where harvest mice were classified as non-detections in both survey years.

There were 86 tetrads that had surveys conducted in both the 2021-22 season and the 2022-23 season. Within these tetrads there were 341 surveys in total, 157 from the 2021-22 season and 184 from the 2022-23 season. This represented a reasonable national geographical spread with at least one repeated survey tetrad from each country but some spatial clumping at county level (see Appendix 1).

Upon comparing all surveys to those specifically within the tetrads surveyed in both years, it becomes apparent that the mean number of nests and the occupancy of surveyed sites remained relatively stable and did not exhibit significant changes. However, when examining the NPHSE index (a specific index related to harvest mouse presence that accounts for survey effort) for both overall surveys and those conducted within repeatedly surveyed tetrads, a notable decline is evident between the two survey years (Table 5). Changes in the NPHSE Indices varied according to habitat with notable increases in ditches and field margins and decline in road verges (Table 6).

Across all surveys conducted in the 2021-22 season, an average surveyor would encounter approximately 2.2 harvest mouse nests every hour of survey effort, translating to approximately one nest found every 27 minutes (calculated as the reciprocal of nests per minute). However, in the 2022-23 survey season, this rate reduced, with only 1.5 nests being discovered every hour, equivalent to one nest found approximately every 40 minutes.

Table 5 *The comparisons of the inter-annual metrics of mean number of nests, NPHSE and occupancy between the two survey years. Calculated using all surveys and only across surveys from the tetrads with surveys conducted in both years.*

	Season 2021-22	Season 2022-23	Change
All surveys			
Mean nests per survey	1.84	1.89	UP
NPHSE	2.2	1.49	DOWN
Occupancy	0.48	0.55	UP
Repeat survey tetrads			
Mean nests per survey	2.78	2.42	DOWN
NPHSE	2	1.17	DOWN
Occupancy	0.55	0.52	DOWN

Table 6 Change in the mean NPHSE Indices according to habitat from first to second survey

Habitat	Survey year 2021-2022	Survey year 2022-2023	Difference
Ditch	9.59	2.92	-6.67
Field	0.71	1.24	0.52
Field margin	6.06	3.00	-3.06
Footpath	0.09	0.61	0.52
Grassland	0.59	1.00	0.41
Hedge	1.57	0.62	-0.96
Marsh	1.05	1.84	0.79
Plantation	1.14	0.50	-0.64
River bank	3.43	2.50	-0.93
Road verge	0.11	3.75	3.64
Rough grassland	2.33	1.41	-0.92
Scrub	0.86	0.81	-0.05
Wet grassland	1.47	1.23	-0.24
woodland	1.08	1.60	0.53

Nest colour

The data on nest colours were quite limited, with only 6.9% of survey nests and 5.6% of presence-only records containing this information. Among the nests for which colour information was available, only 19.6% were derived from the first survey (2021-2022). Within this subset of nests with colour information, most (83.3%) were recorded as "brown". However, green nests were recorded throughout the survey season, suggesting, though unlikely, that harvest mice engage in breeding activities spanning from August to March, and possibly extending beyond this period (Figure 6a). Most green nests were recorded in October and the highest proportion of green nests were recorded from August through December (Figure 6b).

Figure 6 Numbers (a) and per cent numbers (b) of brown and green nests recorded according to the month of the survey for both surveys combined.

Surveyor and coordination feedback

Although fewer surveyors (10 in 2022-23, 68 in 2021-22) and coordinators (4 in 2022-2023, 12 in 2021-22) completed questionnaires after the 2022-23 survey that the previous year, they provided valuable insights on their experiences and perspectives including areas of success and potential improvement for future survey initiatives. Some of the findings are detailed below:

Surveyors

Among the 10 respondents, 20% were members of the Mammal Society. Additionally, 20% were members of local mammal groups, and interestingly, among those who were not members of a local mammal group, 39% expressed a keen interest in joining one. Following their expression of interest in the survey, 70% of respondents received correspondence from the Mammal Society. Additionally, the Mammal Society facilitated connections for 40% of individuals who expressed interest in the survey with local mammal groups. However, of those who were not directly connected, 33% had already established contact independently or did not require assistance.

It is worth noting that 90% of the respondents actively participated in harvest mouse survey training events. Among these participants, 70% were actively involved in conducting or joining surveys and successfully discovered nests. 10% conducted surveys but did not locate any nests, while another 10% reported nest sightings without actively conducting a survey. The remaining 10% cited a lack of available time as the primary reason for not participating in any surveys.

When asked to rate their level of enjoyment on a scale of 1 to 6, most respondents (77%) rated their experience with the survey at the highest level, choosing a score of 6. A smaller proportion (11.5%) rated it as a 5, and another 11.5% rated it as a 4. Ninety per cent of the respondents took the time to review the materials provided on the survey website, and all of them found these resources to be valuable and informative. It was suggested that a simple survey results form/pro forma that is easy to fill out in the field would be helpful.

Lastly, it is noteworthy that all the respondents expressed a strong interest in participating in the upcoming 2023-2024 survey. They also expressed eagerness to receive information about the results from the 2022-2023 survey.

Coordinators

Three of the four respondents were affiliated with local groups, indicating a degree of community involvement in the surveys. Additionally, half (50%) of the respondents were members of the Mammal Society, suggesting a strong connection to the broader network of mammal enthusiasts and researchers. Two respondents went into detail about the number of volunteers involved in their surveys. One reported an impressive 70 volunteers, while the other had 25 volunteers, excluding an additional 40 students who participated in some capacity.

Three of the survey coordinators organised training events. These events varied in size, with nine drawing in a substantial 117 attendees, while another four events had 12 attendees, and a further four had 17 attendees. This commitment to training suggests a dedication to equipping volunteers with the necessary skills.

Three of the respondents reported that they were put in contact with potential surveyors through TMS network. All the coordinators demonstrated a clear understanding of the aims and goals of the survey and believed they had received sufficient lead-in time to prepare for the survey. Notably, none of the survey coordinators received external funding for their efforts.

Encouragingly, three of the respondents expressed their interest in continuing to serve as coordinators in future survey efforts.

Responders also provided valuable feedback on how volunteer participation could be enhanced in the next season. Suggestions included establishing connections with other local interest groups and universities, increasing promotion efforts in Scotland, aiding in finding suitable survey sites, and organizing more training events. Lastly, one responder suggested the implementation of real-time monitoring during the survey season to assess progress and make timely adjustments.

Survey promotion

Between August 2022 and March 23, a total of 23 social media posts were shared across Instagram, LinkedIn, Twitter, and Facebook to inform the audience about the upcoming harvest mouse survey dates and direct them to the registration website. Additionally, reference to or articles about the survey were made in CBBC Newsround, The Times, British Wildlife Magazine, Autumnwatch, BBC Wiltshire radio, the Salisbury Journal and The Guardian (see Appendix 2). Frazer Coomber gave a talk to the Oxford Mammal Group and the survey was featured in Mammal News, the Society's magazine for members, in the Summer of 2022, reflecting on the past survey and looking ahead to the next one, and in Autumn 2022, outlining ways for members to actively participate in the survey. Furthermore, the survey received mention 11 times in Mammal Musings, the Society's E-bulletin, which typically reaches an audience of approximately 5049 individuals. More than 44% of the recipients opened this email, and a substantial total of 771 clicks on the harvest mouse links were recorded over the course of the campaign.

Discussion

There was a greater level of participation in the survey from the first (2021-2022) to the second (2022-2023) year, with a greater amount of effort and more nests being found. This is testament to the effective promotion of harvest mice recording with the formation of a thriving community and indicates the survey's success and its ability to achieve its intended goals. There has been, a notable increase in the coordinator team, which has grown from 19 to 31 members, with a concomitant increase in geographical coverage, allowing the survey to encompass a broader range of locations and habitats. The increase in the number of participants should be considered with some caution. Just like in the first year, the absence of a request for surveyors' names implies that the number is likely an underestimation. However, the increase could stem from an increased willingness to offer names for acknowledgment in the National Survey, prompted by the first year's report. Thus, the count of participants might not necessarily denote a genuine rise in active involvement but rather a greater willingness to disclose personal information. The act of being acknowledged in a survey report carries value, as it provides tangible evidence of volunteer contributions, which can be especially significant for individuals such as students seeking hands-on experience in wildlife surveys. It is noteworthy that the estimated number of participants gleaned from feedback forms provided by coordinators in the first survey closely aligns with the count of individuals identified in the second survey.

A comparison of the data collected between the two survey years reveals a discernible pattern. The larger number of survey groups and participants in the second year has resulted in an increase in survey effort and the amount of data obtained. Interestingly, the only data collection metric that saw a decrease between the two surveys was the number of presence-only records. This suggests that the efforts to encourage more comprehensive surveying and recording have borne fruit. It appears that the approach of motivating participants to not only report biological records but also engage in dedicated survey efforts has yielded positive results, leading to a more comprehensive dataset.

Harvest mouse population and conservation status in Britain

Despite the increase in survey effort, the second survey (2022-2023) did not encompass enough of the historical reference dataset to draw definitive conclusions about the present distributional status of harvest mice in Great Britain. However, the relatively high rates of reconfirmation of hectad presence from the historical dataset and hectads and tetrads between the two surveys, as well as the identification of occurrences beyond their usual range, provide evidence that harvest mice are generally doing well.

The results from the two survey years show some changes in the occupancy indices, albeit not by much. This suggests that, on a survey site level, which approximately corresponds to an area of 100 m², roughly 50% of these sites were occupied. This observation underscores the fact that, even at finer scales, the presence of harvest mice is consistently reconfirmed more frequently than not. The lower percentages of continued presence between hectad, tetrad, and finer spatial units is an interesting observation. Lower continued presence at repeat surveys to, say 100 m squares, may be interpreted as a decline in the species (see Sargent & Pottie, 1997). However, it is also likely breeding animals may not be detected in the same place because they tend to move between local areas within and between years. As a consequence, surveys that return to the same 100 m² site might be construed a methodological limitation to this type of survey work (Roger Trout pers. comm.). Taken this into account, the overall trend implies that the distribution of harvest mice in Great Britain is relatively stable at this smaller scale, albeit somewhat lower compared to larger spatial scales, and is quite positive.

Temporal changes

There is a clear decline in the NPHSE indices between the two survey years. This suggests that this effort corrected index is able to detect trends in breeding success between years and there was a reduction in the relative abundance of breeding harvest mice between years. Such a decline may reflect the year-to-year variation in nest abundance often seen in harvest mice (Trout 1978, Slepstov 1948 in Trout 1978). For example, Lloyd & Kirk (2021) counted the number of nests found in consecutive years at two sites in southern England. According to the nest densities this study found there were high density years in 2004, 2007, 2009, 2014, 2016 and 2018. Although the two sites only overlapped in time between 2014 and 2016, they both showed a high year in 2014 with a subsequent low in 2015. The accumulation of data over future surveys will enable more detailed analyses of the possible effects of weather (temperature, rainfall) on harvest mice breeding directly or indirectly via habitat and food availability.

The effectiveness of the survey in monitoring harvest mice

It is well known that citizen science monitoring programmes benefit from standardised sampling design and adequate observer training (Dambly *et al.*, 2021). There are two standardised monitoring programmes on mammals within the UK that have been running for many years: the NBMP (National Bat Monitoring Programme) and the NDMP (National Dormouse Monitoring Programme). The NBMP has been running since 1996 and feeds information about Britain's 17 species of bats to the Bat Conservation Trust and government to help inform bat conservation. This is a world-leading citizen science programme providing population trends for 11 of the 17 bat species resident in the UK. The surveys are standardised and undertaken by both the public and experienced bat workers on counts from bat roosts and field surveys along waterways, woodlands and in parks and gardens. The NDMP has been running since 1993 and is now the longest running annual, terrestrial small mammal project in the world. A minimum of 50 nest boxes are erected in woods and hedgerows and checked a minimum of two times a year by licensed dormouse volunteers. Box occupancy and changes in box occupancy are used to inform population trends of hazel dormice helping to inform dormouse conservation. These long-term population monitoring programmes also act as an umbrella to smaller more specific projects such as

landscape management and climate change implications (Goodwin *et al.*, 2017; Goodwin *et al.*, 2018), effects of habitat (Harris & Combe, 2018; Trout *et al.*, 2018), genetic and dietary studies (Chanin *et al.*, 2015). Based on the first two years of survey data, the NHMS collects data that could be used to monitor relative population changes like these other long running projects. As such the survey could be considered successful in its ability to monitor not just distribution but potentially abundance indices. Volunteers are key to the success of the survey and with their help our understanding of the population status and conservation needs of this species will improve.

One of the key findings is that this survey can not only identify continued presence in spatial units over several years but also continued non-detections. Such occurrences in areas where harvest mice were previously identified as present from historical records could suggest that specific or localised populations have become extinct. Alternatively, by extending the monitoring range beyond the historic distribution boundaries, this survey can also provide evidence that harvest mice never occurred in certain areas. Both these situations warrant more in-depth study. In the existing atlases, the absence of data often leads to the presumption of absence of the species in those regions, but importantly biological records frequently fail to document non-detections, and these absences are inferred solely on the lack of recorded sightings.

So far, this survey has been able to identify spatial units classified as non-detections in two consecutive years, and this data may be indicative of areas that warrant further investigation for potential harvest mouse release sites. In the UK there is an increasing interest in releasing captive bred harvest mice into the wild to reinforce or reintroduce populations. However, at present releases are conducted on an ad hoc basis without defined protocols or procedures. The TMS harvest mouse steering group suggest that at least two years of pre-release surveys should be conducted at possible release sites and that follow-up surveys should be carried out to see whether releases have been successful.

Given the interest in breeding and releasing harvest mice by zoos and aquaria, and that our recommendation is that potential release sites should be surveyed before any releases of harvest mice are conducted, we have promoted surveys in zoological gardens of members of BIAZA or of organisations that are interested in releasing harvest mice or have conducted releases in the past or bred harvest mice for potential release. Some of the results are as follows:

- Chester Zoo (BIAZA) – Previous release site - surveyed (both years) – continued presence of harvest mice confirmed
- Whipsnade country (BIAZA) – surveyed land – non-detection
- Woburn Safari Park (BIAZA) – surveyed – breeding – presence
- Flamingo land (BIAZA) – surveyed – presence
- British Wildlife Centre – surveyed – released – presence
- Folly Farm (BIAZA) – surveyed (near by 1- 2 km distance) – presence
- Wildwood (kent BIAZA) – surveyed – presence

Until now, releases have been carried out in various ways and often on an ad hoc basis. Not all have carried out pre- and post-release surveys. Consequently, the information gathered here serves as valuable data for pinpointing appropriate release locations and for tracking the effectiveness of past releases.

Survey development

It's important to note, that the occupancy values in the results presented in this report and the previous one should be interpreted with caution. It is highly likely that the presented occupancy values represent an underestimation of the true occupancy. The current method for estimating occupancy remains rudimentary, as it relies solely on calculating presence and absence proportions without factoring in the species' detectability of

field sign presence. The repetition of survey sites both between and within years, particularly in localised spatial units like tetrads, offers the potential for future improvements in data collection. Specifically, it opens the door to the possibility of calculating detectability correction estimates, which could lead to more precise estimates of occupancy.

When recording data, there are still several free text fields that the surveyors need to complete, such as habitat. This gives rise to many unique values which require interpretation and classification into a number of specific categories for analysis. In the future, we plan to adopt a more consistent and existing habitat classification for surveyors, for example UK CEH land cover data, to generate a more consistent approach. This year we looked at nest colour, but recording levels were low making it difficult to interpret the data. Therefore, all surveyors will be asked to make a carefully note of nest colour and, where possible, take a photograph. Hopefully, by recording green or occupied nests we should be able to see whether it is possible to investigate intra- and inter-seasonal trends in breeding times.

Conclusion

Following the success of the first NHMS in 2021-22, the second survey in 2022-2023 aimed to expand the community of surveyors and coordinators, increase the geographical coverage of harvest mouse records and surveys, compare findings between the first and second surveys and so increase our knowledge about the population and conservation status of harvest mice across Britain. The second survey achieved all these aims and bodes well for surveys over the coming years. In particular, the commitment of the surveyors, the substantial amount of time they dedicated, and their meticulous data collection all played a pivotal role in deepening our knowledge of these engaging creatures and their ecological significance.

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Appendices

Appendix 1: Country breakdown of survey data for 2021-2022 and 2022-2023

Measure	2021- 2022	2022- 2023	2021- 2022	2022- 2023	2021- 2022	2022- 2023
	England	England	Scotland	Scotland	Wales	Wales
Survey count	542	726	42	70	1	51
Survey presence	277	437	3	5	1	28
Survey non-detection	256	289	34	65		22
Occupancy	0.511	0.602	0.071	0.071	1.000	0.549
Survey nests	1071	1453	3	9	8	134
Survey effort	1386.567	2412.250	38.350	64.150	20.000	134.783
Average nests	1.976	2.001	0.071	0.129	8.000	2.628
NPHSE	2.384	1.572	0.144	0.112	0.400	2.302
Presence-only records	384	335	7	6	54	36
Presence-only nests	463	449	4	9	51	40
Total nests	1534	1902	7	18	59	174
Total nests (both years)	3436		25		233	

Appendix 2: Key promotion events and activities

National Harvest Mouse Survey 2022/2023 – key promotion events and activities

- 13/05/2022 - Results first broadcast to local groups.
- 27/07/2022 - First [advertised](#) for Year 2 on social media.
- 17/08/2022 - Shared [dates](#) of Year 2 on social media.
- 28/09/2022 - Free webinar about NHMS and first year results, with 96 tickets sold. Video also uploaded to YouTube. Click to see amount of views - https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=25jB_pHdTEI&ab_channel=themammalsociety
 - 29/09/2022 - Press release of first season results released. Sent to 300 journalists at 07.00 via Mailchimp.
- 29/09/2022 - Press release shared across all social media platforms.
- 29/09/2022 Highlighted in Countryside Jobs Service <https://www.countryside-jobs.com/news/weeks-news/2022-09-26>
- 02/10/2022 Highlighted in CBBC Newsround <https://www.bbc.co.uk/newsround/63082257>
- 03/10/2022 Highlighted in The Times <https://www.thetimes.co.uk/article/tiny-harvest-mouse-makes-big-move-as-it-is-found-in-scotland-for-first-time-r5k05slnr>
- Highlighted in Countryside Jobs Service 26/09/2022 <https://www.countryside-jobs.com/news/weeks-news/2022-09-26>
- 29/09/2022 - Appeal re-launched .
- 07/10/2022 - special HM e-bulletin sent via Mailchimp to over 5,000 subscribers.
- 10/2022 – Article in British Wildlife Magazine by Fiona Mathews.
- 24-30/10/2022 - National Mammal Week - various blogs and posts.
- 25/10/2022 - Mentioned in the first 'Watch Out!' lunchtime Autumnwatch programme (towards end) <https://www.bbc.co.uk/iplayer/episode/I0056784/autumnwatch-watch-out-with-hannah-stitfall-and-chris-packham>
- 25/10/2022 - Gareth Harris on BBC Wiltshire Radio, The Breakfast Show
- 03/11/2022 Highlighted in Salisbury Journal <https://www.salisburyjournal.co.uk/news/23096452.salisbury-natural-history-society-wiltshire-mammal-society-search-harvest-mice/>
- Increase in number of news searches for harvest mice in 2022 after press release - see here - <https://trends.google.com/trends/explore?date=2022-01-01%202022-12-31&geo=GB&gprop=news&q=harvest%20mouse>
- 09/01/2023 - Frazer Coomber talk at Oxford Mammal Group, 27 in attendance.
- 20/01/2023 – Highlighted in The Guardian <https://www.theguardian.com/environment/2023/jan/20/country-diary-the-briefest-luckiest-glimpse-of-a-harvest-mouse>
- 17/02/23 Results from first year 2021-2022 survey published in TMS's E-bulletin (over five thousand subscribers) - received 394 direct link clicks.
- 18/02/2023 Survey published across social media channels and received good level of engagement.

Appendix 3: Author Credits

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Thanks to all of our volunteer surveyors, Regional Coordinators and members of the Harvest Mouse Steering Group.

This report should be cited as: Coomber, F.G., Clifton, R, Gilford, E., Alizan, A., Crawley, D., Kirk, S., Lloyd, A.J. & Gurnell, J. (2023). The Mammal Society's National Harvest Mouse Survey: Results from the Second Survey, 2022-2023. The Mammal Society.